

Onodu Atumatijokwu Na Nghotaokwu Na Nzikoritaenzi Agumagy Nke Si N'aka

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Vmiedemede

Agumagy dika mpaghara nzikoritaenzi, na-akowapya nghota. O biaziri buru na agumagy by nke e ji nka pyr9 iche wee na-ezipya site n'ijiri atumat9okwu mee nkea. Ya mere na at9mat9okwu na-ach0 ka a na-akpachapyr9 ya anya ma na-akowakwa ya n'ydj pyr9 iche. Na nghotaokwu, at9mat9okwu na-ar9 9r9 site na mgbatl nghota nke sitere na nwete echiche malite. Na echiche gbasara aka karfa, at9mat9 okwu met9tara ngwa (devices) di icheiche nke pyr9 iche na nghotaokwu ma9by n'yt0asysy.

Nkowaokwu: Nghotaokwu, Nzikoritaenzi, Agumagy, At9mat9okwu

Mmalite

Tupu ndi nchocha a gaa n'ihu n'or9 a, 9 di mkpa ikowat9 okwu ndi ga-enye aka ighota ihe a naede.

Nghotaokwu: Nghotaokwu by ngalaba Sayensi Asysy (Lingwistiks) nke na-eleba anya na mpytara okwu na ahir9okwu n'asysy gasi n'ydj pur9 iche. Saeed (2007) kowara nghotaokwu dika Omymy mpUtara nke e ji asysy ezipya. Ndimele (2007) na nke ya, kowara nghotaokwu dika ngalaba Sayensi Asysy na-elebanye anya na mkpyr9okwu na ahir9okwu n'asysy. Site na nkowa ndi a niile, nghotaokwu na-ahy maka etu ndi mmady si eji asysy ezikorita ozi n'agbanyeghi na nkea by naani mpaghara 9r9 Nghotaokwu n'inyocha etu ndi mmady si aghota mpytara.

Nzikoritaenzi: Nzikoritaenzi by yzo mmady na ibe ya si emekorita ma9by zikorita ozi, akparamagwa, mmetyta, mbamuuru, dgz., site n'okwu cny, ide ihe, ma9by kwany yzo Obyla Oz0.

Asụsụ bụ the pụtakarịchara ihe e ji ezi ozi. Martinez na Nosnik (1988) kowara nzikorịtaozi dika usoro/uz9 mmadu na ibe ya ji abiak9ta gnu site n'ozu, ma tukwaa anya ka e nwee nzaghachi, atumatuobi (opinion), ihe omume ma9bu akparamagwa. N'aka nke 9z9, Chiavenato (2006) naak9wa na nzik9ritaozi bu usoro e si ewefe ozi na ngh9ta, site n'aka otu wee ruo na nke onye 9z9. Ya mere na nzikorịtaozi niile ga-emetutariri mmadu abu9, onye na-ezipu ozi na onye nke na-anara ya anara.

Agymagy: Dika Nwadike (1992) si k9waa ya, agumagu bu okwu sitere na Latin "literae" nke bu 'letters' pulite. Agumagu nwere mputara/ngh9ta abu9; ha bu ndia:

- i. Ngh9ta izugbe, nke putara ihe 9bula e dere ede, dika Joografi, Akukoala, S9m, Fiziks, Kemistri, dgz.
- ii. Agumagu dika aka9ru nke e sitere na ya wee na-ak9waputa ma na-ahu ndu.

Na nch9cha a, nk9wa agumagu nke abu9 ka a na-ekwu maka ya. Agumagu nwere nnukwu ngalaba abu9; agumagu 9dinaala (gnu) na agumagu ugbua (ederede). Nke 9bula n'agumagu ndia na-adi n'udi akuk9 (iduuazi), ejije na abu.

Atymatyokwu: Atumatuokwu bu asusu nka e ji agbati ngh9taokwu/ahiriokwu nke puru iche na ngh9ta nkiti. Ya bu okwu/ahiriokwu nwere Atumatuokwu na-aputakari ihe n'agumagu iji mee ka 9 ghara ibu okwu umuaka ma weputakwa ihe a ch9r9, site n'iru 9ru a ch9r9 ka 9 ru9.

Ntyleghari Agymagy

Agumagu dika mpaghara nzikoritaozi, na-akowaputa ngh9ta. O biaziri buru na Asusu edemede bu nke e ji nka puru iche wee ziputa site n'ijiri atumatu okwu mee nke a. Ngh9ta ndi nke sitere n'atumatuokwu abughi mpaghara di iche iche nke ya bu okwu. Ya mere na atumatuokwu na-ach9 ka a na-akpachapuru ya anya ma na-ak9wakwa ya n'udi puru iche.

Na ngh9ta9kwu (Semantics) atumatuokwu na-site na mgbati ngh9ta nke na-ebute ubara echiche (polysemy) ma9bu nwefe ngh9ta (transfer of senses). Ya mere, a na-ahutakari atumatu okwu dika nke sitere na mburu. Na ngh9ta gbasara aka, atumatuokwu mettgara usoro/ ngwa niile nke sitere na ngh9taokwu ma9bu ut9asusu.

Dika Platt (1977) siri k9waa, atumatuokwu bu nke na-adachapu na lingwistik n9ms n'asusu a naasu kwa ub9chi n'uf9du uz9, ikekwe na ngh9taokwu, ma9bu usorookwu. igbapu n'usoro a

(deviation), nwere ike, 9 gaghị abycha n'udị ịda iwu. O nwere ike buru ịji oke ndokO dika na nkwanwe. Ebumnuuche nkaasYsY bY idokO ma kOwapYtakwuo mgbagha (arYmarY) ịji nwee mmelita oke (emotion) nke ndị OgbakO (audience). AtYmatYokwu/nkaasYsY ndị nke metgara nke mwube agYmagY, nwetara nka ha site n'atYmatY (strategies) ndịa.

1. Ndika (Analogy/Imagination)
2. Mwube KeYtOasYsY (Grammatical Construction)
3. Okwuozizi (Indirectness)
4. Mputara Nsinauda (Sound Effects)
5. Myiwere (Similarity)
6. Ndiche (Contrast)
7. &kwU (Association)

Site na nkOwa nke Plat (1977) atYmatYokwu ndị nke metgara nka nwube agYmagY bY ndị e kewara n'udị ar

1. Attmatt Kendika (Analogy/Imagination):

Ndị abY atYmatY na-ewepYtaiji ndika ekwu okwu site n'iwepYtaechiche dī n'ihe ndi na-anOghl n'ogbe, ihe ndi no nso n'ihe gbasara agYmagY. AtYmatY okwu ndi a ga-ahY ebe agYnyere:

Nkwusara (Apostrophe): Nke a bY okwu a na-ekwuru onye anOghl ya, ihe a naghl ahY anya maObY onye nwuru anwY ka a ga-asl na onye ihe ahY nO ebe ahY mgbe ahY a na-ekwu ya. O by n'aby ka atYmatY okwu a kacha apYta ihe. QmYmaatY:

Dike, OnwY egbuola gi

OnwU gi gbara onye ObYla gharil

OnwU gburu gi,

Egbuola OtYtY mmadY.

Mmemmadt (Personification): MmemmadY bu atYmatY okwu na-ewere ihe adighl/enweghl ndY dika ihe ndi nwere ndY (mmadY). E werezie ihe ndi ahY na-adighl/enweghl ndY na-ekwu okwu, 9

dị ka 9 bV mmadV ka ana-ekwu. QmVmaatV sitere na Chukwukere (2006) n'abv ya 'Obiri N'elu Akwa' ihu akwykwO 35

ÒkOò (ahiri 54)

Ga-aja Vnù eze 9cbi (ahiri 55)

Egbeokwu (Hyperbole/Exaggeration): Egbeokwu bU atYmatV okwu e ji ama atV ihe ma ihe a naama atV ya anaghị aharḡ ka ihe e ji ama atV ya. E nwere ike Isị na 9 bU okwu e ji etu OnV. QmVmaatV – Chukwukere (2006) n'abu ya 'Ekaite Eketala Oke', ihu akwykwO 86

... Nwa m af9 iri na ise (ahiri 45)

Agh99la agadi narị iri na ise (ahiri 46)

Atymatu Mwube Keytoasysy (Grammatical Construction): E nwere VfOdij iwu ndi nke a nabatara n'odidi ahiriokwu n'asysV Olg. Ha mebere iwu VitOasysV. Etu o sina di, VfOdij n'ime ha bu iwu ndi nke e nupurḡ isi na ha maObV e sooro n'Vz9 purḡ iche, iji nweta ebumnuuche ndi a ch9r9. AtYmatV okwu mwube keIgoasysV ndi pVtara ihe gUnyere ndla: AjVjV Nzaraonwe (Rhetorical Question), Ntimkpu (Exclamation), NdOghari (Inversion), Orurughaokwu (Climax) na Mgbudaokwu/Mwetuokwu (Anti-climax).

Ajuju Nzaraonwe (Rhetorical Question): Nke a bu asysV nka e kwuru n'Vdi ajVjV nke na-adighi Osi. Q bu ajVjV a na-ajV ka okwu odee wee gbanyekwuo mgbOrOgwV maObV ime ka e nwekwuo nkwenye okwukwe n'okwu odee. QmVmaatV – Chukwukere (2006) n'abv ya 'Ekaite Eketala Oke'

Ilekwere Lō ya? (ahiri 93)

Ihukwara 9kwa Lō ya? (ahiri 94)

Ntimkpu (Exclamation): Nke a bu okwu mmapVta (sudden), nkwupVta mmetVta obi (passionate address), nke e ji akOwapVta mmetVta obi, di ka:

- Ewoo! Okwu agwYla!
- Efuo m oo!

Ndoghari (Inversion): Nke a bu mgbanwe n'ekere ma9bu ezi usoro okwu, iji nweta nkwusi ike/nkwusigide (emphasis). Ezigbo usoro ahiriokwu Igbo bu Isiahiri - Ngwaa – Nnara (SVO), mana e nwere ike tvgharia ya, isiahiri ewerezie onodu ikpeazu. (mumaatg:

- a. Ns9 ka Jehova di
Usoro ahiriokwu a kwesiri inwe bu 'Jehova di ns9'.
- b. Ut9 ka okwu gi di, nke tosiri ibu 'Okwu gi ut9'.

Orurughaokwu (Climax): A na-enweta orurughaokwu site n'ime ka okwu ndi nke kara di mkpa kpeta azu ma okwu ndi nke mkpa ha pekasiri na mpe bute uz9. (mumaatg:

- a. Ndi be ha bu ogbenye 9nu nty ma mgbe niile iga ala Bekee ka 9 na-akpu n'onu
- b. (gugu asusu na-ebute odide ya uz9

Mgbydaokwu/Mwetuokwu (Anti-Climax): Nke a bu azu (opposite) orurughaokwu. (bu usoro e ji eme ka okwu ndi nke ka mkpa bute ndi nke mkpa ha di pekasiri mpe uz9. E ji orurughaokwu enweta nkonume (suspense), ma jiri mgbudaokwu enweta nche n'ihu miry iche (special focus). (mumaatu:

- a. Dinta gbagburu agu tagburu ewu ya.
- b. O jiri ugb9ala bido 9rg Bekee, mechaa gbawa 9gbatumtum, ugbu a 9 lara ezumiike nka, 9 na-agazi ukwg ala.

Atymatu Keokwuozi (Figures of Indirectness): Atymatv ndi a ga-atgle ebe a bu ndi nke na-egosiputa ihe ma9bu echiche okwuozi. Ihe ha na-aryty aka na-enye aka iweputa ihe ndi mebere agumagu. Ndi putara ihe ebe a gunyere: Nkwuma (Euphemism), (gharaokwu (Irony), Haipoleji (Hypallage), tkpe Mkpekii (Innuendo/Insinuation), tkpe (Satire), Zuguma (Zeugma)

Nkwuma (Euphemism): Atymatv okwu a bu usoro e ji uz9 di iche iche na uz9 na-ato ut9 na nti were na-ak9wa okwu di nj9 ma9bu okwu siri ike. (bu okwu 9ma e ji ekwudaru okwu 9j99 ala, ma I leruo anya nkeoma, i ga-ahu na 9 bughu ezigbo ihe ka a na-ekwu maka ya. Ihe e ji na-eme nke a bu ka a hapu inwe ihe mwute ma9bu luwa ugu. (mumaatg:

- a. Nwoke ahu ataala 9ji.

b. Okeke anaghị eji ihe dị na nwaanyị egwu egwu.

Qgharaokwu (Irony): Nke a bụ okwu ọ na-abụ e kwuo ihe ọzọ, e buru ihe ọzọ n’obi. Dịka aha ya siri dị, ọ bụ okwu ọ na-abụ e kwuchaa, nghọta ya ahapụ etu e siri kwuo ya, tugharia na-ekwu ihe ọzọ. Omụmaatụ Chukwukere (2006) n’abụ ya bụ ‘Ekaite Eketala Oke’, ihu akwukwo 88

Loya abughị onye ọrụ ugbo (ahịrị

90) Loya bụ okpe ikpe (ahịrị 91)

Ikpe nkwumọọto (ahịrị 92)

N’abụ ya ‘Obiri N’elu akwa

Ikpe mkwumọọto (ahịrị 1)

Gbara ọto kpee ikpe

Ebubo ụgha

Mkpọomasị enweghị

aha **Haijpleji (Hypallage):**

Na haijpleji, a na-ebuga nkowaaha site n’ebe aha o kwesiri ikowa, buga ya n’okwu ọzọ dị n’ahiriokwu. Omụmaatụ:

a. ‘O dere leta na-ama jijiji’ kama isi na ‘O jiri aka na-ama jiji dee leta’.

Ikpe Mkpekii (Innuendo/Insinuation):

Nke a bụ okwuozi (indirect speech) na-egosi na ihe e kwuru bụ ihe mgbaru ihu nyere ihe e kwuru maka ya. Omụmaatụ:

a. Onyeisi tosiiri ima kari ndi ọzọ

b. Otu mkpuruokwu ezuorala onye maara ihe.

Ikpe (Satire)

Ikpe b⁹ okwu mgbar^y ihu nke ndi nka ag⁹mag⁹ na-eji ak⁹wap⁹ta ihe ndi mmad⁹ na-eme. Okwu di etu a b⁹ iji kwaa ndi nke a metytara emu, ma buru n'obi na ha ga-enwety mgbanwe. OmUmaatU:

Ab⁹ odinaala a b⁹ ab⁹ ikpe.

‘Anjelina lawa alawa

Ç laa leeti

O jewe ejewe

O jee leeti... dgz

Zuguma (Zeugma):

Zuguma na-ab⁹ mgbe e weere okwu di mfe dee ihe metytara 9n9d9 ab99 ndi 9z9 ebe 9 bu na okwu ah9 dabara naani n'otu n'ime okwu ab99 ndi ah9. Ihe a b9 mgbe a na-ejiri otu ngwaa dee maka ha ab99.

a. Gh⁹tuo mkpUrUosisi ndiah⁹ na ndi nwe ha

b. T⁹⁹ umUnwoke ndia na 9⁹ ha mkpOr⁹

Atumatu Kemputara Nsinuda (Figures of Sound Effects)

Ogo nke mb⁹ e ji ahazi as⁹s⁹ b⁹ usoro 9daas⁹s⁹ (sound system). N'ezie, a na-esite n'9da (9daume na mgbochiume) emebe mkpWVokwu. A na-esite na mkp9ryokwu emebe ahiriokwu ma sitekwa n'ahiriokwu nweta edemede. O b9kwazi 9da okwu di iche iche ka e si na ha enweta mpUtara (effects) ndi nke b9 na 9 b9 site n'9ry ag9mag9 ka e si enweta ha. Ha na-abia site n'9z9 ndia:

- i. Biambiamgbochi (Alliteration)
- ii. BiambiamUda (Assonance)
- iii. Nsin99da/9da9da (Onomatopeia)
- iv. UrOokwu (Pun/Paronomasia)
- v. Ndak9rita (Rhyme).

Bjambjammgbochi (Alliteration)

Nke a bu asusu nka a na-enweta site n'ikwunwo (repetition) uda mgbochiume yiri onwe ha n'okwu ha na ibe ya nodowere. Omumaatu

- a. Papa Pita patara popo panye papa Pol.
- b. Nwaanyi no n'ukwu mgbamgba gbagharĩa ba mgbamgba

mgba. Bjambjamuda (Assonance)

Nke a bu nkunwo (repetition) uda udaume yiri onwe ha n'okwu ya na ibe ya nodowere. Omumaatu:

- a. Nwaanyi na-akwa akwa kwara akwa na okuko yiri akwa n'elu akwa a kwara akwa
- b. Taa okpokoro oka taa oka okpokoro

Nsinuuda/Udauda (Onomatopoeia)

Nke a bu nghota e si n'uda ihe dara na-enweta. O bu okwu e si n'uda ha enweta mputara (meaning) ha. Omumaatu Chukwukere (2006) n'abu ya Ekaitē Ekētala Okè, ihu akwukwo 85

Ha niile n'ime abo ahia wawom (ahiri)

7) Ama ririri. (ahiri 42)

Urọokwu (Pun/Paronomasia)

Ihe a bu atumatokwu na-egosiuta iji okwu ndi uda na nsupe ya na ibe ya bu otu ma mputara ha di iche. Urọokwu na-eweta mputaraokwu (ambiguity) n'ebe okwu no. Omumaatu:

- a. Nwaanyi na-akwa akwa (sews) na-akwa akwa (is crying) na okuko yiri akwa (laid eggs) n'elu akwa (clothes) o kwara akwa (sewed)
- b. O na- ala n'ala nna ya na-ala n'iyi. (ala – returning, ala – land, ala –

wasting) Ndakorita (Rhyme)

Ndakorita bu ebe e nwegasiri uda yiri onwe ha no na ngwucha nkejiokwu nke ahiri abu. Omumaatu:

Lekwa ka ha pYtara
 JUwa ma 9ha Omatara
 Ihe mere na ha ezuchaghī
 Mekwara na ha amachaghī
 Mgbe ihe niile jiri gafere

Enwerendak 9ita na ‘pytarara 9matara, ‘ezuchaghī’ na ‘amachaghī’

Atymaty Myiwere (Figures of Similarity)

Nke a bY at 9mat 9okwu ebe a na-atYle myiwere dī n’etiti ihe, echiche, na kwa OnOdy ndī nke dī adī na ndī nke na-adīghī adī. At 9mat 9okwu ndī nke pYtara ihe ebe a gYnyere:

- i. Myiri (Simile)
- ii. MbYrU (Metaphor)
- iii. Allegory (Nkonilu)/ V kabYilu (Parable/Anecdote)

Myiri (Simile)

Myiri bY at 9mat 9okwu e ji egosipYta na ihe na ibe ya yiri/ihe dī ka ibe ya mana 9 byghī na ihe abY9 ahY e ji atYnyere ibe ha bY otu kp9mkwem. Ebumnuuche at 9matuokwu a bY iji mee ka 9gy9/odee wepYta myiri dī n’etiti agwa ihe ndī a na-atYnyere ihe 9z9. Okwu ndī e ji eme nke a bY dīka na ‘ka’. O bu okwu e ji ama at 9 etu mmad 9/ihe na ibe ya siri yie. OmYmaatV

- a. Nwoke ahU dī ka ezi.
- b. O jOrO njO ka

UsU. Mbyry (Metaphor)

Nke a bY at 9mat 9 okwu na-ak 9wa na ihe ahY a na-ekwu maka ya bu ihe ahY kp9mkwem. OnOghī na ntYnyere dīka myiri siri dī.

QmYmatY – Chukwukere (2006) n’aby ya ‘Nwanyīzie’, ihu

akw 9kw 9 i (Q)chīchī abYrU īgba(ahīī 18)

Obodo ab9r9 igba (ahiri 26)

Nkonilu (Allegory)/Vkabyilu (Parable/Anecdote)

Nkonilu/Ijkab9ilu b9 ilu e tinyere n'obere ak9k9. Ndi Igbo na-ak9 ya n'9di ilu iji wee kowaa ma9b9 ch99 okwu mma. ijkab9ilu 9b9la nwere ihe kpatara e ji k99 ya ma nweekwa ngh9ta pur9 iche a ch9r9 iji ak9k9 ah9 wee zip9ta. 9m9maat9:

Otu nwa mm99 na-ach9 mmad9, were 9z9 h9 ozu nw9r9 anw9, wee tie'Ehee', si na ije ebeerela ya nkenke.

Nkowa:

Nke a p9tara na mmad9 inweta ihe 9 na-ach9, t9madi n'at9ghi anya

ya. Atymatu Kendiiche (Figures of Contrast)

Ndi a b9 as9s9 nka ndi e sitere n'ihe banyere ndiiche n'echiche ma9b9 n'odidi nweta. At9mat9 ndiiche ndi pigara ihe gunyere:

- i. Nhagideokwu (Antithesis).
- ii. Akp9okwu (Epigram)
 - i. Igbuduokwu (Paradox)
 - ii. Oksm9r9n (Oxymoron)
 - iii. Silepsis (Syllepsis)

Nhagideokwu (Antithesis)

N'at9mat9okwu a, okwu e kwuru ekwu na-ahagide ibe ya. Nhagideokwu bu okwu 9b9la na-ab9ghi otu na ngh9ta, na-ekwugide onwe ya. O na-eme ka okwu e kwuru wee p9ta ihe nke9ma. Om9maat9:

- i. Nwata i kpor9 ji 9s9 na ije abia.
- ii. Lee akpa m z99r9 gi, tufuo ya ma i ruo n'9l9akw9kwo.

Akplokwu (Epigram)

Nke a b⁹ okwu amamihe na-agbagha onwe ya. A naghⁱ aghOta akp⁹okwu site n'ile ya anya n'elu n'elu. E kwuo ya, mmad⁹ leruo anya ala nkeOma, ⁹ghOta ya. OmUmaatU:

- i. O b⁹ nwunye Okoro ji ya nd⁹
- ii. Nwata a b⁹ na ezinaUO ha na-eri nri.

Igbuduokwu (Paradox)

Igbuduokwu b⁹ atYmatY okwu ⁹na-ab⁹ e kwuo, ⁹dⁱ ka e nweghⁱ ihe ⁹b⁹la nwere isi dⁱ n'ime ya, ma ⁹b⁹ry na e chebara okwu ya echiche nkeOma, a ga-ach⁹p⁹ta amamihe juru na ya.

OmUmaatU:

- c. Onwu gbuo mgbaru, e nweghⁱzi onye a ga ejere mgbaru.
- d. Ij^bOchⁱ onye ara maara na ⁹na-awⁱ ara ka ⁹ga-akw^ysⁱ i^wi ara.

Atumatu Kenkwu (Figures of Association)

Ndⁱ nke a b⁹ atYmatY okwu a na-enweta site na mmekOrⁱta okwu na ibe ya nwere. MmekOrⁱta a nwere ike dⁱ n'etiti ogbe ihe na mpaghara (ak⁹k⁹), ihe na ihe ya na ya so, ma⁹b⁹ kwan⁹ OnOchi anya otu. AtYmatY Kerⁱkw^u a ga-eleba anya ebe a g^unyere ndⁱla:

- i. NrUtUaka (Allusion)
- ii. Antonamasⁱla (Antonomasia)
- iii. AhaOnOchi (Metonymy).
- iv. Mpaghara OnOchi (Synecdoche)

Nrutlaka (Allusion):

Nke a b⁹ okwu na-arYtY aka na mmemme ma⁹b⁹ n'onye a ma ama. E nwere ndⁱ nke sitere na Baⁱb^ul. OmUmaatU:

- i. Onye a b⁹ Shakespeare nke ag⁹mag⁹ Naⁱjirⁱla
- ii. Daniel abatala n'ogb⁹ ikpe.

Antonomasia (Antonomasia)

Nke a bY iji aha onye a ma ama (nke a r9r9 ar9 ma9bY omere eme) ji gosipYta òtù ma9bY mmàdY. OmUmaatU:

- a. OkammYta ndi a bYcha Jones na Chomsky nke sayensì Asysy n'etiti anyi.
- b. Edozie bY Maradona n'ime ndi aniile gbara b99y taa.

Ahaonochi (Metonymy)

AhaOnOchi bY mgbanwe di n'aha, ebe a naghi akpO ihe aha, kama aha ihe e jiri mara onye ahY. OmUmaatU:

- a. Mkpìsìedide (onye nta akYkO/odee/OkammYta) karìrì mma agha (onye soja).
- b. Nyemoolo abY9 kam fty9 (ihe n'ime oloolo).

Mpaghara onochi (Synecdoche):

Na mpaghara OnOchi, mpaghara ihe nwere ike inOchite anya ihe ahY ma9bY kwanY ihe ahY n'ukwu anOchite anya mpaghara ya. OmUmaatU:

- a. Akaniletinye akan'oy.
- b. Naljirìla (ndi b99y Naljirìla) meriri Cameroon (ndi b00y Cameroon).

Nchikota na Mmechi

N'ichikOta ma mechie nchOcha a, onye nchOcha depYtachara ma kewasìchaa atYmatYokwu ndi a dika 9r11 ha siri dìgasì.

Asysy agYmagY bY nke pYrY ihe. O na-eji 9tyy asysy nkà enweta ihe 9 ch9r9. Asysy nka ndla bY ndi na-esite na mpYtara nkwy (associative meaning) nke ahìrìlokwu nwegasìrì. Etuosiladì, o teela aka ototo n'ime ato matO ndi a bYrYla ihe a nabatarala iji na-eede ihe ma na-asYkwa n'ywa gbaa gburugburu.

Edensibja

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